

STRATEGIES FOR TURNING INDIA INTO A VIKSIT BHARAT BY 2047

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Abstract

The issue of *Viksit Bharat* is a new concept. Though the term is the Hindi version of Developed India, the Prime Minister took the opportunity to popularize the terminology among the general citizens of this country with a special focus on the youths and students. The students and young people are full of vigour and vitality. They are the main force behind any change in society and country as a whole. The primary aim of the Prime Minister's introduction of this term is to Indianize the development process in every sphere of society. However, the concepts of developed India and *Viksit Bharat* have subtle differences, because the new concept aims to bring about a lofty ambition in India by attaining a \$30 trillion economy within a particular timeframe, i.e., by 2047, when India celebrates its 100th year of Independence. But the task is not easy at all. It is very challenging indeed. Despite that, the Government and the majority of the people are committed to achieve the vision of Prime Minister. As the country at present has not any clear roadmap for attaining the goal, that is why this author conducted a research to trace out the strategies that might bring about the Vision *Viksit Bharat* by 2047.

Key Words: Prime Minister of India, *Viksit Bharat*, strategies for *Viksit Bharat*, a \$30 trillion economy, Developed India

Introduction

The term '*Viksit Bharat*' is the Hindi translation of the English word 'Developed India.' The Prime Minister of India very carefully took up the Hindi terminology *Viksit Bharat* to put a special focus on the indigenous model of national development. By using the Hindi term, the Prime Minister sought to invoke the spirit of patriotism blended with national development through capacity building and skill development of the young generation people in India. After discussing the concept '*Viksit Bharat*', we will endeavour to find out the strategies that might turn India from a Medium Human Development country to a very High Human Development country. Now, Let us now discuss the concept of *Viksit Bharat*.

The Concept of *Viksit Bharat*

Vision '*Viksit Bharat*' is the current government's mission to turn India into a completely developed nation by 2047. Before the 18th general, the Prime Minister concluded a meeting with his Council of Ministers to discuss the new government's action plan in the next 100 days after the formation of the government. In the said declaration, the Prime Minister stated that "...The core objective of the *Viksit Bharat* vision is to foster inclusive economic participation among all citizens. A key component of this initiative is the ambitious goal of elevating India to the rank of the world's third-largest economy within the next five years (by 2030), contingent upon the NDA assuming power once more. Goals set under the mission are to turn India into a \$30 trillion developed economy in about two and half decades for a projected 1.65 billion population. The document envisions economic growth, sustainable development goals, improvements in the ease of

living and doing business, enhanced infrastructure, and bolstered social welfare initiatives" (*Deccan Herald*, 2024). Further, "Viksit Bharat 2047" is the current government's roadmap to making India a completely developed nation by 2047, 100 years after independence. Mr. Modi has stated that "The core objective of the *Viksit Bharat* vision is to foster inclusive economic participation among all citizens" (*Deccan Herald*, 2024). But the question is: how will the vision of PM Modi be realized? Is there any blueprint for achieving the goal? The answer is 'No.' Therefore, with a view to attaining the Goal, a concrete bunch of strategies have been prescribed after extensive research. But the road is not rosy, rather it is full of multifarious challenges. Despite various challenges, let us examine how India can attain the target.

1. Arouse Love and Respect for India

Always love and praise for India. Mark Twain, a renowned American novelist, once said, "India is the cradle of the human race, the birthplace of human speech, the mother of history, the grandmother of legend, and the great-grandmother of tradition. Our most valuable and most constructive materials in the history of man are treasured up in India only" (Mandal, 2024, p. 51). This proves that India is a great country with a rich culture, tradition, and scientific discoveries for centuries. Further, Raman Singh writes in a recent article that Albert Einstein went one step ahead in acknowledging India's contribution to world civilization, wherein he remarked: "...we owe a lot to the Indians, who taught us how to count, without which no worthwhile scientific discovery could have been made" (Singh, 27 Jan. 2023). Similarly, the great Indologist Max Muller once said, "If I were asked under what sky the human mind has most fully developed some of its choicest gifts, has most deeply pondered on the greatest problems of life, and has found solutions, I should point to India" (Singh, 27 Jan. 2023). Further, Henry Beveridge (1867, Preface) in his famous book *A Comprehensive History of India, Civil, Military and Social From the First Landing of the English, to the Suppression of Sepoy Revolt; Including An Outline of the Early History of Hindoostan, Vol. 1* wrote: "India, the most valuable dependency of the British crown, is also one of the most interesting portions of the globe. Even some of its physical features are on a scale of unparalleled grandeur. The stupendous mountain chain along its northern frontier, rising gradually from a plain of inexhaustible fertility, has snowy summits that tower nearly six thousand feet above the loftiest of any other country in either hemisphere; while over the vast expanse of its magnificently diversified surface, almost every product possessed of economical value grows indigenously, or having been introduced is cultivated with success."

2. Let Us Learn From America

We can learn from the story of America about how to increase income and how Indian people can become billionaires. In this regard, we can highlight the assertions of Robert E. Wright, who wrote in a recent article: "Undoubtedly, Americans made many other improvements in 1802 that escaped the author's notice. But the real story behind America's 19th-century growth miracle lay not in the details of corporation formation, particular inventions, or the proliferation of innovative practices or better breeds, breads, or meds...they believed their lives and property were their own, to do with as they wanted and not exposed to expropriation by their neighbours, foreign politics, or their own governments" (The Daily Economy, 2020).

3. Let Us Learn from China

China is the second-largest economy in the world. And both China and India gained independence almost simultaneously. So, we cannot ignore China, a big economic giant. Here, a few words can

be shared in regard to the astonishing development of China, and our takeaway from China. Every Indian student who is studying in any educational institution must keep "Competitiveness" in mind. China follows competitiveness as a mantra development. Hence, Indian people should also take up the idea of 'competitiveness' to excel the global economic giants.

4. Let Us Take a Lesson from Japan

Japan's economic growth is miraculous. In this regard, Masahiro Takada writes: "The rapid economic growth in Japan from the beginning of the 1950s to the early 1970s not only resulted from special government policies and revolutionary events but was also achieved by the cumulative effort and hard work of the people. The unique characteristic and ability of the Japanese people to imitate and improve the skills learned, and then apply them to their own system, was the most important factor for their successes... One of the factors that the Japanese made use of their unique characteristic to expand the economy was to improve and make practical use of technologies and technological know-how imported from foreign countries" (Takada, 1999, p. 12).

5. Role of One Party and Formulation of Stronger Policies

Behind the development and growth of every country, there remains strong government policies. In this regard, Professor Md Zafar Alam Bhuniyan (Bhuniyan, 2019), in a recent article pointed out that: "During the miracle years, the voters continued to elect members of one political party, the Liberal Democratic Party, thereby avoiding the political unrest that hurt the economies of other nations during this time." Indian electors may consider such a strategy for the welfare of the country and its people. The policies and strategies are very important in shaping the future of a country. In Japan, "The policies and strategies were set forth carefully by the policy-making authorities to protect and sustain the growth, and therefore the Japanese political system had a major role in its development as well" (Takada, 1999, p. 15).

6. How the Government can Increase Its GDP @10 Per Cent?

It is not that India's economy will automatically increase in its own way. Besides, the making and growing of a few hundred billionaires will not make India a developed nation. For that reason, the income growth of the majority of its population should be ensured. We do not need lopsided growth; rather, we require holistic and inclusive development. All the Ministries of the Union Government, as well as State Governments, have to work hand in hand and shoulder to shoulder to achieve the goal of *Viksit Bharat*. India's GDP should continue at the average growth rate of 10 or 11 percent. If you look at Japan in the 1960s, you will find that "Although a few problems arose from heavy industrialization, this plan has contributed greatly to the latter half of Japan's rapid growth with an average growth rate of 10.8 percent in the late 1960s and drove the economy to become the second largest in the world by the year 1968" (Takada, 1999, p. 15). Indian policymakers should also focus in a similar way on the GDP growth rate.

7. How the Number of MSMEs Can Be Increased?

As per the information of the Ministry of Micro, Small, and Medium Scale Industries, at present India has "1,05,21,190 number units in the total small scale industry sector" (Ministry of Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises, 31 July 2023). This number will have to be increased by at least threefold, i.e., at least 3 crore small-scale industries should have to be set up in India by the year 2047. The Ministry of Micro, Small and Medium-Scale Enterprises should give a target to the

District Magistrates and Sub Divisional Magistrates to set up MSMEs proportionately under their jurisdiction. Make a plan to set up at least 300 new MSMEs in every subdivision every year. Every district should recruit experts in industrial development and posted them to the Sub-Division level offices. China has maintained its position as the world's manufacturing powerhouse for the last 15 consecutive years.

8. Drone Manufacturing and Export Should be Increased

The Indian government must allocate more money in budgets for its defence manufacturing units; it should encourage and fund the private drone manufacturers, and India must develop homegrown drone technology for national security. "Drones now are not just about surveillance. They need to carry payloads, drop bombs, execute kamikaze missions. That requires integration between drone intelligence and explosive intelligence" (The Economic Times, June 11, 2025). Drones might be manufactured through both private and public partnerships, as is being done by Adani Group's Alpha Design Technology and Israel's Elbit Systems. Drones must be used for both civilian and defence purposes. Indian scientists and researchers should devote themselves to developing AI hardware, without which software superiority won't be sufficient. In the end, it can be said that "India needs a dedicated Cyber Command, built like those of the US or Israel. One that can detect, defend, and -when needed - disrupt" (The Economic Times, 11 June 2025). Export of drones in smaller and medium-sized countries in Europe, Asia, and Africa will increase India's revenue and foreign reserves.

9. How Can India Expedite Its Nuclear Power

According to Stockholm International Peace Research Institute, "Of the total global inventory of an estimated 12,241 warheads in January 2025, about 9614 were in military stockpiles for potential use. ...Russia and USA together possess around 90 per cent of all nuclear weapons" (Stockholm International Peace Research Institute, June 16, 2025). The data available in the World Nuclear Forces, January 2025, indicated that the USA is the most powerful country with a total deployed warhead of 1770, while Russia has 1,718. In 2025, the USA's military stockpile is 3700, it is 4,309 for Russia, while the UK possesses only 225. But France has 290, and China, with over 600 military stockpiles, holds the 5th position. On the other hand, India, a democratic country, possesses only 180 nuclear warheads, while Pakistan has 170 military stockpile. SIPRI estimates that "China now has at least 600 nuclear warheads. China's nuclear arsenal is growing faster than any other country by about 100 new warheads a year since 2023. But by January 2025, China had completed or was close to completing around 350 new ICBM silos in three large desert fields in the north of the country and three mountainous areas in the east (SIPRI, 6 June 2025). Therefore, to compete with China, India must allocate more funds to the defence budget, increase research and development, and also manufacture at least 150 to 200 new warheads every year to match with Big Three Countries such as the USA (3700), Russia (4309), and China (600).

10. Foreign Investors Should be Incentivised to Come and Invest in India

There is heavy demand for good and cheap medical devices in India. Still, we are dependent on good-quality medical devices. Let us manufacture qualitative medical devices in India. "A majority of India's medical devices, ranging from a simple thermometer to cotton wool and electrocardiograph (ECG) machines to catheters, are imported, and up to 11 percent of them from China...In certain device categories, Chinese imports are as high as 87 percent of total imports"

(Porecha, Businessline, 19 June 2020). The Government of India must incentivise the foreign investors to set up individual or partnership industries of factories in India.

11. The Indian Government Must Respect Pluralism and Adopt Inclusionary Policies

Can a bird fly with one wing? Can a human being be born with one parent? If a bird cannot fly without two wings and a child cannot be born without the union of two opposite genders, then how can India grow and develop fully without the active participation of both men and women, and the Hindus and Muslims? Without the whole-hearted participation of the fifty percent population, i.e., women, India's dream of a *Viksit Bharat* is next to impossible. Similarly, without the participation of the minority communities, such as the Muslims, Christians, and Buddhists, the dream of India to become a *Viksit Bharat* is sure to be an enigma. As both women and girls are integral parts of the human population, both Hindus and Muslims are also equally important components of the Indian social fabric. Women and girls, as well as the Muslim and backward populations, are very important assets of society. They must not be ignored and excluded from the mainstream development agenda. The United Nations indicates that "The empowerment of women and their full participation on a basis of equality in all spheres of society is fundamental for development" (The United Nations General Assembly, 1997).

12. India Must Develop and Utilize the Skills of Talented Youths

The Wheebox India Skills Report 2023 suggests that in 2023, 50.3% of young people are found to be highly employable overall. The percentage of the employable women workforce has increased to 52.8%, compared to 47.2% for men. The report also points out that 89% of graduates were actively seeking internship opportunities. The survey indicates that candidates from Uttar Pradesh, Maharashtra, and Delhi had the highest employability. "Amongst B.Tech, MBA, and B.Com were found to be the most employable talent from amongst various domains. Mumbai, Lucknow, and Mangalore were the cities with the most employable talent, and the most preferred cities for work by graduates were Bangalore, Chennai, and Delhi/NCR. The world is rapidly aging, but India is still young. In the next few decades, India will be a talent powerhouse and one of the largest contributors to the global workforce" (The Economic Times, 29 December 2022). This means India does not have a shortage of skilled workforce. The government of India must take care of our skilled young people.

13. How Can India Attract More Foreign Direct Investment

Though after the economic reforms in the 1990s of the last century, foreign direct investment has increased in India, still it is not as much as in China and the other top four economies in the world. "In 2004, India received FDI inflows of around 0.5 percent of GDP, whereas China received FDI worth 3.2 percent of GDP. In dollar terms, China received 16 times the FDI as India in 2004 (Jain-Chandra, IMF eLibrary, p. 73). In an article, Sonali Jain-Chandra points out that, "At the same time, investor surveys point to a strong interest in India as a destination for FDI. Investor surveys by the United Nations Conference on Trade and Development (UNCTAD) and A.T. Kearney in 2004 and 2005 place India as the second most attractive destination for FDI" (Jain-Chandra, IMF eLibrary, p. 73). However, the consecutive governments have not been able to translate this into actual FDI inflow. As per the World Economic Forum, 2005, 'India's overall infrastructure quality ranks low,' and "The significant burden of bureaucratic red tape and regulation in India further worsens the investment climate. For instance, it takes 89 days to start a business in India, more than double the time required to start in China. The enforcement of contracts takes longer in India

(425 days) than the average in the sample. Also, once in business, firms find it difficult to exit" (Jain-Chandra, IMF eLibrary, p. 78). In addition to these, the labour market is volatile, trade unionism is strong, and extortion by politically supported goons is one of the reasons that hinders

14. Rural Youth Must be Encouraged to Participate in Nation Building

The Prime Minister called upon the BAPS volunteers to continue their service-oriented efforts, directing them to work towards the goal of transforming India into a developed nation by the time it celebrates 100 years of independence in 2047. His vision of a prosperous and developed India resonated with the attendees, urging them to play an active role in the nation's growth. He also told the *Karyakars* to follow the *Ghar Sabha* popularized by Pramukh Swami, which is actually praising and respecting each other in a family. "Prime Minister Narendra Modi on Saturday (8 December 2024) urged citizens to become the force behind the country's march towards the target of "Viksit Bharat 2047" and announced that next month a "Viksit Bharat Young Leaders' Dialogue" would be held to give the youth a platform to exchange ideas" (The Tribune, 2024).

In addition to the above strategies, some more policies can be adopted by the government for the achievement of a \$30 trillion economy by 2047. These include population control first. Rae considers that, "The necessity for regulating population comes, of course, from the limitation of the natural resources at society's command..." (Rae, 1891). Self development is another aspect that the citizens should pursue. Swami Vivekananda said, "It is easy to point out the defects of institutions, all beings are more or less imperfect, but he is the real benefactor of humanity who helps the individual to overcome his imperfections under whatever institutions he may live. The individuals being raised, the nation, and its institutions are bound to rise" (Vivekananda, 2013, p. 48). Moreover, the state must ensure equality, promote friendship and love for all sections of people. Subhas Chandra Bose pointed out that, "In order to ensure equality, we must get rid of the bondage of every kind, social, economic, and political, and we must become fully and wholly free. But freedom does not imply the absence of law. It only means the substitution of our own law and our own discipline. Discipline imposed on us by ourselves is necessary, not only when we have attained freedom, but it is more necessary when we are struggling to achieve freedom. Therefore, discipline, whether for the individual or for society, is necessary as the basis of life" (Saggi, 1954, p. 46). Our former President, Dr. APJ Abdul Kalam, was very much impressed with the concept of *Ghar Sabha*, articulated by Pramukh Swamiji of BAPS. Dr. Kalam wrote in his famous book- *Transcendence: My Spiritual Experience with Pramukh Swamiji* (2015, p. 111) that, "Pramukh Swamiji has articulate five principles which promote family unity: meet each other; praise and appreciate each other; recognize and acknowledge the talents and virtues of youth family members, particularly encouraging children by appreciating them; help each other; and, above all, exercise forgiveness." I do believe that all the family disputes and ill feelings toward each other in a family or in a society can be removed by following the principle of *Ghar Sabha* at home or in the locality where we live.

To cope with the modern world, more and more Students should learn Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics Subjects. Space research, space technology, robotics, drone making, drone repairing, and drone playing youths should be there in lakhs of families. Every young Indian student today will have to take an oath to study hard, learn modern skills such as computer hardware, software, manufacturing, machine learning, and the use of AI, etc. Also, they should become very high-quality entrepreneurs, explorers, scientists, researchers, authors, bankers,

tax consultants, teachers, farmers, political leaders, and spiritual leaders. Remember, only following religion will not give you food, and only hard work without following religion will never produce quality work. So, my suggestion is to work hard with sincerity and honesty by remembering God in your mind. An average Indian student's aim should be to earn at least Rs. 2.5 lakh per month by 2047. Therefore, the Indian people should live like saints and work like lions. A lion possesses mighty power and is considered the king of the forest, yet it has to run after its prey to maintain its livelihood. Hence, all people must be hard-working like Dr. APJ Abdul Kalam and ambitious like Elon Musk.

Conclusions

From the above discussions it can be concluded that establishing peace and living together with harmony in society is very vital. Also, leading an ethical, spiritual, and disciplined life is equally important. Whatever works we may do, whatever gender and colour we may have, and wherever we may live; if we work very hard with sincerity for the benefit and profit of the institution, organization, or person for whom we work; if we look after our children and family members as per our capacity, and give love and affection to our children, respect our elders, parents, and teachers; if we meditate daily and practice yoga or do some physical exercise, or play some outdoor games; if we extend our helping hand towards our relatives, friends, colleagues and neighbours; if we refrain from illegal and unethical activities such as stealing, extortion, taking bribes and harming others for narrow personal gain, our country will turn into a Heaven on Earth. It is proposed that, both the Union and state governments should act proactively to turn India from a developing country to a developed one by 2047. For this purpose, policy reforms, wherever necessary, must be done forthwith to actualize the vision *Viksit Bharat*. It is a fact that, there is diversity in the region, political faith, size, nature, and capacity of the states and Union Territories. Despite all the limitations, forgetting all personal and political differences, all the stakeholders should come forward with a single goal to transform our into a Viksit Bharat by 2047.

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